

Personality traits and career preference of nursing students in St. Dominic College of Asia: Basis for career counseling and psychoeducation program

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Abstract

This paper intends to find out the personality traits and career preference of 106 Nursing students using International Personality Item Pool Big-Five Personality Factor Markers (IPIP Big-5) and Holland's Career Inventory. Career theorists like Gottfredson (1981) and Holland (1959) contend that personality traits and career or occupational choice must be fit or congruent to predict good adjustment, work enjoyment, and optimum achievement of goals. Such being the case, the two abovementioned variables are correlated. Results showed that the personality traits of the respondents are Neuroticism (78.30%) and Conscientiousness (70.7%) while their career preference are Social (70.75%) and Investigative (58.49%). There is medium correlation between personality and career choice ($r=0.41$).

Keywords: Personality traits; career preference; nursing students; career counseling; psychoeducation.

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Introduction

In the career decision-making process, Kemboi et al. (2016) noted that "personal internal characteristics" or personality traits are least considered or at times totally not included. Career theorists agreed that there must be suitability of personality traits and work environment so that work can be performed successfully (Gottfredson, 1981). Similarly, success in one's career is highly reliant on the match or compatibility between one's personality traits and job requirements (Judge et al., 1999). Indeed, there must be alignment or synergy between personality traits and careers or vocational choices to produce optimal goals. In addition, Holland further contends that personality inventories include interest, career, and vocational inventories. In this paper, the researchers intend to explore the personality traits of 106 nursing students at St. Dominic College of Asia using the International Personality Item Pool Big-Five Personality Factor Markers (IPIP-Big 5) together with their career interests using Holland's Career Interest (RAISEC) and find out if they are matched or correlated.

Theoretical Framework

This research was guided by John Holland's trait and factor theory, where trait refers to personality type, which ideally must be congruent with the course of study (environment), which serves as the factor that may contribute to the easy adjustment, thriving tendency, and success of the student in his or her field of study and consequently career. John Holland's trait and factor theory (1959) theorized that there are six personality types, namely: 1) Realistic, 2) Artistic, 3) Investigative, 4) Social, 5) Enterprising, and 6) Conventional, which are based on a person's interests and personal characteristics. Since the respondents are nursing students, the congruent personality types include Social and Investigative types since the nature of the nursing profession includes altruism, social adeptness, and providing nurturing (for the social type), but also requires being analytical, fact-based, and empirical.

In addition, Goldberg's big five-factor trait theory includes extraversion, agreeableness, openness, conscientiousness, and neuroticism, which he describes as culture universal, thereby linking the trait theory of personality to the evolutionary model (Goldberg, 1992). Goldberg's personality trait theory presupposes that personality traits are related to many aspects of life, including the choice and endeavor of one's vocation or career.

Review of Related Literature

Personality of Nurses

Eley (2012) delved deeply into the personality traits of nurses and their reasons for entering the nursing profession. Researchers utilized mixed-method sequential explanatory designs, specifically the use of semi-structured interviews. Instruments used include validated personality inventories that measure temperament and character traits.

Two themes emerged, namely "*opportunity for caring*" and "*my vocation in life*," which were evident in key temperaments and character traits of the participants; more specifically, their scores revealed a higher level of empathy and altruistic ideals. Researchers then concluded that the caring nature of the nurses is definitely the principal quality of their personalities.

Chang et al. (2016) aimed to find out what personality dimensions of nurses are apt to promote or ensure patient safety. Using 421 full-time nurses in the medical facility as respondents, the researcher found out that nurses' personalities contribute to patient safety as they enable nurses to find ways to improve job performance, which includes ensuring patient safety. Researchers suggested the integration of the personality trait "*Openness to experience*" in the hiring criteria because such a trait can positively impact patient safety.

Yazdanian et al. (2016) attempted to find out if nurses' personality characteristics are associated with their attitude towards the elderly. It was a cross-sectional method, with 261 nurses selected as respondents through stratified sampling techniques. Instruments used were Kagan's Attitude Towards Older People Scale (KAOPS) and the Five Factor Personality Inventory. The statistical methods used were descriptive and inferential statistics, specifically the Pearson-R test of correlation and multiple linear regression. Results show that nurses with high agreeableness and lower neuroticism can be an appropriate option for caring for the elderly.

Kemboi et al. (2016) intended to find out if there is a significant relationship between personality types and the career choices of 399 undergraduate students at Moi University in Kenya. His simple quantitative survey research utilized two instruments, namely: 1) a questionnaire adapted from Holland's Self-directed search and 2) Holland's Occupational Finder Checklist. The researcher anticipated that the findings of the research would serve to enhance the understanding of career types in students' career planning and the development of career guidance and counselling in both secondary school and university. They concluded that the appropriateness of personality and career choice among students would result in easy adjustment and enjoyment while taking their preferred course.

Bhatti et al. (2018) contend that this prominent feature of personality traits, when aligned with job requirements, will yield work achievement and success. Using the 5-factor model of personality, they came up with a few propositions: 1) the tendency to be successful in academic and scientific areas such as science, research, and engineering is among students who are high in openness to experience; and 2) in business context, those who are low in neuroticism personality traits are more likely to excel in non-profit sector careers. They concluded that the propositions needed to be validated and further suggested the use of personality tests when recruiting.

İspir et al. (2019) used descriptive and correlational studies in their research entitled "The relationship of personality traits and entrepreneurial tendencies with career adaptability," involving 265 Junior and Senior nursing students. Their instruments are: 1) the Student Information Questionnaire; 2) the Career Adaptability Scale; 3) the Personality Inventory; and 4) the Scale of University Students' Entrepreneurship.

They found out that the prominent personality traits of their respondents were high conscientiousness and low emotional stability. However, there is a weak to moderate correlation between personality traits, entrepreneurship, and career adaptability.

Terry et al. (2019) identified the personality traits of 1,982 nursing students to find out which personality traits would make them more likely to pursue a career in rural areas. Researchers used a validated questionnaire to identify personality traits as well as rural practise intentions. The cross-sectional research design was utilised to reveal the importance nursing students place on undertaking rural careers. Findings of the study include that the personality traits of nursing students who envisioned themselves working rurally after graduation are those who have a lower level of neuroticism but possess a higher level of conscientiousness and agreeableness. Obviously, students with a higher level of neuroticism were less likely to consider rural practice as a future career pathway. Researchers state that nursing students' personality traits are contributing factors to their preference for urban and rural practice.

Kim et al. (2020) examined the effect of the fit between personality and core job characteristics on job crafting. The researchers utilized NEO-FFI and conducted a survey of 200 college students. A polynomial regression analysis was used to test the effects of the fit between personality and job characteristics on job crafting. They concluded that when both openness to experience and job characteristics are congruent at high levels, the tendency to proactively perform one's tasks is also high (Kim et al., 2020).

Although several studies were conducted to predict the levels of personality traits and career preferences of Filipino students independently (Datu & Buenconsejo, 2021; Fuente, 2019; Llenares et al., 2021), no studies in the Philippines were made to correlate the variables. Therefore, this study aims to find out the correlation between personality traits and career preferences of students in a higher education institution in the Philippines, particularly those who are enrolled in the Nursing program.

Statement of the Problem

1. What are the personality traits of first year and second year students enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Nursing?
2. What are the career interests of first year and second year students enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Nursing?
3. Is there a significant correlation between personality traits and career preferences of first- and second-year BSN students?

Methodology

This research study utilized a descriptive-correlational method. According to Siedlecki (2020), correlation designs aim to determine the relationships between many variables in a single study. However, the limitation is that the study cannot describe how relationships exist. Purposive sampling was used, as it was intended to recruit specific participants to take part in this research study (Campbell et al., 2020). A total of 108 first- and second-year students who are enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Nursing at St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines, were involved in the study.

Instrumentation

This study utilized a research questionnaire that was adapted from Goldberg’s IPIP-Big 5 (International Personality Item Pool Big-Five Personality Factor Markers) and John Holland’s Career Inventory Test. IPIP-Big 5 by Goldberg (1992) consists of a 100-item version measuring the Big Five Personality traits, namely openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. The IPIP-Big 5 has been found to have good internal consistency and is strongly related to the NEO-Five Factor Inventory’s (NEO-FFI) major dimensions of personality. The instrument is applicable to a wide age range, that is, from 16 to 83 years old. John Holland’s Career Inventory Test, or RAISEC career test, consists of 180 items; the six career interests are Realistic, Artistic, Investigative, Social, Enterprising, and Conventional (Holland, 1959).

The research questionnaire was made through Google Forms, and it was disseminated to the students via e-mail and the Blackboard Learn application. The data were gathered, tallied, and evaluated using a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to determine the level of personality traits and career preferences of nursing students. On the other hand, a Pearson-R correlation was used to show the correlation between the two variables.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Personality Traits of Nursing Students (n=106)

Personality Traits	VL	%	L	%	A	%	H	%	VH	%
Openness to Experience	0	0.00	15	14.15	41	38.68	34	32.08	16	15.09
Conscientiousness	0	0.00	1	0.94	10	9.43	20	18.87	75	70.75
Extroversion	5	4.72	9	8.49	38	35.85	39	36.79	15	14.15
Agreeableness	0	0.00	5	4.72	54	50.94	32	30.19	15	14.15
Neuroticism	0	0.00	0	0.00	6	5.66	17	16.04	83	78.30

Legend: VL - Very Low; L - Low; A - Average; H - High; VH - Very High

Table 1 shows the very high and high scores of first- and second-year Nursing students in the dimensions of IPIP Big 5. The respondents scored very high on the traits of Neuroticism (83 = 78.30%) and Conscientiousness (75 = 70.75%). The neuroticism personality trait revealed the tendency to be worrisome and anxious, emotionally unstable, and self-blaming (Goldberg, 1993). Those who have a higher level of neuroticism least consider rural practice as their future career pathway, but high agreeableness, conscientiousness, and open-mindedness are personality traits that may contribute to nursing students’ decision-making regarding their choice of location when they practice their profession (Terry et al., 2019). The neuroticism personality trait unquestionably must be low when one is considering the nursing course and profession (Yasdanian et al., 2016; Terry et al., 2019). Conscientiousness, on the other hand, revealed one’s inclination to be prepared, orderly, and disciplined.

In the high category of scores of the respondents, Extraversion is the highest (36.79%) followed by Openness to Experience (32.08%) and Agreeableness (30.19%). Few behavioral indicators of Extraversion are the tendency to be out as well as fun-loving, friendly and warm.

Openness to experience personality trait is manifested in the tendency to be interested in variety, disciplined, orderly, and independent (Bhatti et al., 2018). In addition, McCrae and Costa (2008) singled out the sense of curiosity, open-mindedness, and acceptance of novel experiences possesses by individuals with high openness to experience trait. Although openness to experience would very much suit jobs such as advertising, research, and artistic occupations, Chang et al. (2016) found out that high level of openness to experience among nurses enable them to find ways to improve job performance, which include patients’ safety. Such findings made them conclude that to positively impact patients’ safety, there is a need to assess nurse’ openness to experience, and perceived time pressures. They also recommended to include nurses’ openness to experience into hiring criteria. Agreeableness is manifested in one’s tendency to be sympathetic, trusting, and supportive (Bhatti et al., 2018). Yazdanian et al. (2016) concluded that the appropriate personality type of nurses when caring for elderly is those who are high in agreeableness and low in neuroticism.

Taken together, the very high percentage of neurotic personality among respondents (83 students = 78.30%) raised the question of whether it is really a trait or a state. A high level of neuroticism among nurses would mean high sensitivity even to normal situations and intolerance to novel and difficult events manifested in emotional reactivity. However, the question is: is the respondents’ high level of neuroticism a trait or a state? A trait is illustrated as having more stable, solidified, and enduring characteristics or patterns of behavior, while a state is a more fleeting and temporary way of being and behaving (Biggs et al., 2017). Due to external factors like the impact of the pandemic on students and other disruptions, it may be probable that contributing factors to their high level of neuroticism are external factors and not necessarily their internal personality characteristics.

Table 2. Career Preferences of Nursing Students (n=106)

Career Preferences	VL	%	L	%	A	%	H	%	VH	%
Realistic	0	0.00	3	2.83	13	12.26	50	47.17	40	37.74
Artistic	0	0.00	3	2.83	10	9.43	37	34.91	56	52.83
Investigative	0	0.00	3	2.83	10	9.43	31	29.25	62	58.49
Social	0	0.00	3	2.83	6	5.66	22	20.75	75	70.75
Enterprising	0	0.00	3	2.83	16	15.09	32	30.19	55	51.89
Conventional	0	0.00	3	2.83	16	15.09	35	33.02	52	49.06

Legend: VL - Very Low; L - Low; A - Average; H - High; VH - Very High

Table 2 shows the high and very high scores and percentages of the respondents in their career interests. With very high scores, the respondents top three are social (70.75%), investigative (58.49%), and artistic (52.83%). Social-type personalities choose professions that are altruistic, helping, and nurturing, like teaching, nursing, and counseling. They value helping people and are therefore often perceived as helpful, friendly, and trustworthy. Eley (2012) found out in her research that the nurses’ primary intention in choosing the nursing profession is altruistic ideology (to provide quality care and assistance for others), and personality-wise, her respondents are high in empathy and altruism as measured by her validated instruments, namely the personality inventory, which measures temperament and character traits.

Indeed, the social type of preference of the respondents who are nursing students is the essence of congruence theory, as is the personality (social type) and nursing course (environment) fit (Kemboi et al., 2016). The second rank, which is the investigative type, is associated with being scholarly, as they are good at analysis and have an intellectual and scientific inclination. They enjoy exploring a vast amount of academic work, experimentation, research, and mathematical or scientific activities. In addition, they are fond of documenting new knowledge, finding and understanding issues, and finding solutions to common problems (Kemboi et al., 2016).

Table 3. Correlation Between Personality Traits and Career Preferences

Personality (x)	Career (y)	x+y	x ²	y ²
16	40	640	256	1600
75	56	4200	5625	3136
15	62	930	225	3844
15	75	1125	225	5625
83	55	4565	6889	3025
	52			2704
204	340	69360	13220	19934

N = 106
r = 0.421 (Medium Correlation)

Table 3 shows the medium correlation between personality and career preference of the respondents (r = 0.42). This finding supports ample research conducted highlighting the significant relationship between personality and career choices (Hussain et al., 2012; Kemboi et al., 2016; Owusu et al., 2023).

The respondents' very high score in neuroticism (78.3%) can be partially attributed to ample reasons, particularly some external factors. For instance, the profound negative effects of the pandemic and the macro and micro aggression brought about by social media contribute significantly to the mental health conditions of many people, regardless of their age. Being new students in school (freshmen and transferes) would also mean an adjustment to the school culture, which would undoubtedly cause negative feelings such as nervousness, feeling overwhelmed, and anxiety. In addition, being young (ages 18 to 19), they are obviously limited in their coping abilities due to their limited knowledge and experience (Barlow et al., 2014). Hence, it is probably that their high neuroticism is not an inherent personality characteristic or trait but can be considered a temporary and fleeting state of being (Biggs et al., 2017).

The next high score, which is conscientiousness, which is the tendency to do one's work systematically and with quality, may compensate for the negative effects and disturbances of the nursing students-respondents. Conscientiousness is also described behaviorally as being careful, diligent, orderly, and efficient. Indeed, the high conscientiousness personality trait among nursing students at St. Dominic College of Asia is an advantage because it is needed as the profession requires a high level of carefulness and diligence in order to be considered efficient and effective as a nurse (Terry et al., 2019).

With regards to the career preferences of the respondents, social (70.75%) is the highest with 75 out of 106 students. The nursing profession fits the social dimension because nursing's nature of work includes providing for and taking care of patients health and wellbeing and requires empathy and altruism. Investigative (58.49%) also fits the nursing profession because being analytical, scientific, facts-based, and having the ability to document new knowledge and understanding derived from ample cases of human physical predicaments are highly required among nurses to thrive in their profession.

Conclusion

Respondents obtained very high scores on two dimensions of personality traits using the IPIP-Big 5. They are neuroticism (78.3%) and conscientiousness (70.7%), while their career preferences using John Holland's Career Inventory Test are social (70.75%) and investigative (58.49%). There is a medium correlation between personality traits and career preferences (r = 0.421).

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